

Research Article

**Comparison of Incidence of Thyroid Dysfunction in Post-Menopausal Women,
Pre-Menopausal and in Diabetics and Non-Diabetics**

¹Andleeb Zehra, ²Salwa Ejaz
and ¹Mehreen Zainab

¹UHS, Lahore.

²Mohiudin University AJK

ABSTRACT

Objective: To know the incidence of thyroid problems in patients with diabetes mellitus in different populations is inconsistent and in the general population.

Background: The summative effect of dysfunction in thyroid and diabetes in the age of menopause may have special modification to the normal configuration. The profile of the patients with thyroid can provide an association between diabetic women and post-menopausal thyroid at various ages. To compare total thyroxine (TT4), (FT4) free thyroxine, thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), total triiodothyronine (TT3) and in free form (FT3) in postmenopausal, non-diabetic postmenopausal and postmenopausal women who are diabetic the study was designed for comparison.

Methods: From Multan, Pakistan a total of 77 women were selected and divided into 3 groups: postmenopausal nondiabetic (n = 33), diabetic postmenopausal (n = 32) and premenopausal (n = 13) non-diabetic for the study purpose. Samples of the Serum participants were collected with consent on written after counselling and thyroid parameters given were analyzed by ELISA technique.

Results: In postmenopausal diabetic women TT4 was significantly higher in comparison with women who are premenopausal. In cases of diabetes, FT3 and total triiodothyronine are lower significantly than non-diabetic postmenopausal women. Compared with postmenopausal diabetic cases, free triiodothyronine level was higher significantly in cases of premenopausal.

Conclusion: It is concluded that Thyroid gland stimulate its capability in non-diabetic and diabetic postmenopausal patients. Nevertheless, work in a larger population must have a clear idea.

Key words: Premenopausal, diabetics, Thyroid profile, postmenopausal.

INTRODUCTION

Endocrine organs, thyroid especially, with aging may have very important changes functionally. In the general population diseases of the thyroid are common and with increasing age have higher incidence rate. The major changes of function result in the reduced iodine uptake of the thyroid gland, T3 and T4 release, reduced synthesis of free T4 and increasing T3 inverse images are provided, with concomitant reduction of TSH remaining normal or higher in both sexes [1, 2, 3]. The greatest thyroid dysfunction risk is due to aging is more consistently in women.

Clinically It is usually absolute because the signs and symptoms appear mostly are familiar to those associated with aging. The menopausal effect in thyroid is because of aging. The expression of thyroid disease can be change after menopause, the autoimmune type especially. Thyroid gland have no effect on the pathogenesis related to direct menopause-related problems, but hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism are known to be associated with menopause complications such as atherosclerosis, osteoporosis and heart problems. Thyroid dysfunction has been found to be very

common among women having thyroid disease with age 50 or above, so to recognize thyroid disease it is important in old age thyroid disorders. In addition, women who are postmenopausal have high risk of developing thyroid dysfunction and various complications which can worsen this risk most probably [4].

In a survey, Japanese women between age of 36-60 years, similarities between symptoms of thyroid dysfunction and menopause, even before menopause, were demonstrated. Therefore, it is considered necessary to differentiate between the symptoms of menopause and thyroid disease. Therefore, elderly women are recommended to be excluded in the period of climacteric to exclude thyroid disease sub clinically. The incidence of disease of thyroid has been found to be variable in diverse population of diabetes mellitus in the general population and in patients. In diabetic postmenopausal women the study was not done in population locally. This study is an attempt to examine the status of thyroid functionally in postmenopausal diabetic patients of different ages [5, 6, 7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted, in part, at the Multan Social Security Hospital and partly at the Molecular Medical Research Center (CRIMM), Nishtar Hospital, Multan. The study was approved by Nishtar University Human Research Ethics Board, Multan. A total of 65 postmenopausal women were selected through favorable sampling according to the age of one hundred and fifty postmenopausal cases, diabetic and non diabetic age. All patients were divided into three groups: post-menopausal diabetes (n = 32), post-menopausal (n = 33) and non-diabetic menopausal (n = 13). The participation criteria for all subjects are postmenopausal women with age > 30 and type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2). Non-diabetic patients were included in the control group to compare with non-diabetic subjects. Written informed consent of each participant was obtained prior to clinical examination and collection of samples.

Approximately 5 ml of blood was taken from each volunteer. Samples were immediately placed in EDTA anticoagulant tubes between ice packs and CRIMM was transferred to N.UM Molecular Biology Laboratories. Serum samples can be stored and analyzed using collectable labeled, micro-ELISA AccuBind selectable marker (serum TSH, TT4, TT3, free T4 and ST3). SPSS 21 version was used for data entry and analysis.

RESULTS:

Serum TSH mean levels were almost similar to pre-menopausal diabetic and non-diabetic postmenopausal united close proximity. There was a significant but insignificant increase (8.6%) in TSH when compared to non-diabetic men before menopause in non-diabetic subjects after menopause. There was no difference almost in TT4 serum levels between the two postmenopausal conditions. However, TT4 mean serum levels in these 2 cases were higher compared to pre-menopausal concentrations. It was not significant that the non-diabetic TT4 increase was significantly higher in post-diabetic menopausal conditions compared to the pre-menopausal phase (Table 1). Serum TT3 in postmenopausal diabetic patients was reduced by postmenopausal and non-diabetic women. In diabetic patients, the TT3 ratio is 32.0% lower than controls of non-diabetic. In non-diabetic pre-menopausal controls, concentration of TT3 is 9.1% lower than menopausal women and non-diabetic. This significant non-diabetic issue was lower in postmenopausal patients (25.3%) compared with premenopausal (Table 1). In mean serum levels of T4 in the static diabetic there was no difference when have comparison with the pre-menopausal and non-diabetic stage. The FT4 mean value was approximately 8.1%, but not significantly higher in non-diabetics than in non-diabetics. ST3 concentration in diabetic subjects, their controls have been 35.9% lower than non-diabetic after menopause and the difference was significant statistically. In diabetic premenopausal controls, the concentration of hormone was $02.8 \pm 0.5\text{pg / ml}$; For this reason, the level was 12.4%

lower than non-diabetic postmenopausal women, but it was not statistically significant. On the other hand, hormone levels were 78% higher in premenopausal subjects than in diabetic postmenopausal subjects (Table 1).

Table-1: Pairwise comparison of study variables

Variables	Pairwise comparison					
	Pst Mp N	Pst Mp D	Pst Mp N	Pre Mp N	Pst Mp D	Pre Mp N
TSH μ U/mL	4.1 $\pm$ 0.7	3.9 $\pm$ 0.4	4.1 $\pm$ 0.7	3.7 $\pm$ 1.0	3.9 $\pm$ 0.4	3.7 $\pm$ 1.0
	p = 0.54		p = 0.74		p = 0.99	
TT ₄ μ g/dL	13.0 $\pm$ 0.3	13.1 $\pm$ 0.2	13.0 $\pm$ 0.3	12.4 $\pm$ 0.3	13.1 $\pm$ 0.2	12.4 $\pm$ 0.3
	p = 0.96		p = 0.62		p = 0.05*	
TT ₃ μ g/mL	4.8 $\pm$ 0.2	3.3 $\pm$ 0.2	4.8 $\pm$ 0.2	4.4 $\pm$ 0.3	3.3 $\pm$ 0.2	4.4 $\pm$ 0.3
	p = 0.00*		p = 0.83		P = 0.05*	
FT ₄ μ g/dL	2.0 $\pm$ 0.1	2.1 $\pm$ 0.1	2.0 $\pm$ 0.1	1.8 $\pm$ 0.3	2.1 $\pm$ 0.1	1.8 $\pm$ 0.3
	p = 0.69		p = 0.87		p = 0.87	
FT ₃ μ g/mL	2.3 $\pm$ 0.4	1.5 $\pm$ 0.2	2.3 $\pm$ 0.4	2.7 $\pm$ 0.4	1.5 $\pm$ 0.2	2.7 $\pm$ 0.4
	p = 0.05*		p = 0.89		p = 0.04*	

*p-value significant (<0.05)

Pst Mp N= postmenopausal non-diabetics

Pst Mp D= postmenopausal diabetic

Pre Mp N= premenopausal non-diabetic subjects

DISCUSSION:

It is now well known that thyroid dysfunction increases with age and is more frequent in women. It is usually clinically obsolete because the symptoms are usually similar to those associated with aging. Thyroid disease is a common finding in most types of diabetes and is usually associated with DM2, especially with age. An Australian study emphasized the presence of subclinical hypothyroidism (8.6%) in DM2 women. However, in DM2 women with no known thyroid disease; Subclinical hypothyroidism has been widely seen, but as a coincidental finding; For this reason, the routine screening of thyroid function in DM2 is controversial. In this study, the teeth approaching the postmenopausal period were assessed in terms of the activity of the thyroid gland. A group of premenopausal individuals were compared in a similar way to understand postmenopausal adaptations in the context of premenopausal status. In the study population, TSH did not show any significant difference in age in a number of comparison groups. Similarly, a recent study of elderly individuals reported that, in addition to the effects on the T3 and T4 fractions, the TSH concentration tended to be normal or both cinste concentrations tend to be higher. In contrast,

significant changes in TSH concentration have been reported in one study, resulting in an age-related physiological decline in TSH in the absence of subclinical autoimmune hypothyroidism with increasing age. However, the investigators found no feedback response in terms of their effect on total and free levels of thyroxine, and reported that the mechanism was unknown.

There is a possibility that the decline in TSH may be due to reasons other than adaptation to aging. This assumption supports the observation of this work. A study in elderly Jews showed significantly higher median serum TSH concentration than younger controls. This study has been observed in relation to TSH. For this reason, this study suggests that TSH concentration in circulation is not significantly affected during non-diabetic and non-diabetic postmenopausal events. The results of TT4 in this study suggest that TT4 levels in postmenopausal diabetic subjects are significantly higher than those premenopausal. Simple non-reproductive aging was the reason for a significant difference between the postmenopausal and non-diabetic menopausal groups. For this reason, diabetes appears to be the most likely cause of higher TT4 than premenopausal status. Of course, the non-urogenous phase probably reduces the use of thyroxine. High values of T3 and T4 and inadequate secretion of TSH in old age are associated with a reduced sensitivity to the negative effect of thyroid hormones in women with the pituitary gland.¹¹ This is the expression of the free fraction. Therefore, the increase in TT4, FT4 is the increase in TT4. For this reason, it is assumed that progesterone is a possible factor for TT4 increase, as observed in the present study. Total T3 was almost identical in premenopausal and postmenopausal cases, but was significantly lower in postmenopausal women than in non-diabetic women in the diabetic group. For this reason, it is clear that the type 2 diabetic condition expected to be due to insulin resistance reduces TT3 levels. Circulation is the result of deiodination in the epithelium of the TT3 thyroid follicle or in various target tissues of TT4. There

are other studies reporting that TT3 is decreasing in T2DM. T3 and T4 levels were reported to be significantly lower in patients with T2DM compared to diabetic healthy subjects and that TSH levels were significantly higher than in diabetic healthy subjects.¹² This study has two low TT3 probabilities. One of these is the inhibition of moniodinase, which converts TT4 to TT3 and the other metabolism of TT4 into rT3. In both cases, the goal is the mechanism of deionization.

The rT3 concentration will provide more detailed information to make sure that metabolic pathways are mainly monitored in postmenopausal diabetic subjects. However, this study shows that TT3 is significantly reduced during diabetic postmenopausal events, so the assessment of thyroid activity and the necessary treatment in these people will undoubtedly be beneficial for improving health conditions. T4 did not exhibit the free part. There was a significant difference in the non-diabetic and non-diabetic postmenopausal cases and in the general population of non-diabetic menopausal subjects. In postmenopausal diabetic patients, FT3 concentration is significantly lower than non-diabetic subjects. This is also lower than the premenopausal group. Decreased TT3 and postmenopausal women are directly associated with the free fraction as FT3 in the diabetic state. The decrease in FT3 may be a consequence of the reduction in TT3, especially as in T4, and is supported by research data in which the free fraction is positively correlated with the total fraction of hormone. Another possibility is that the deiodination of FT4 in FT3 is likely to be reduced relative to the reduced activity of the moniodinase concerned. Remarkably, a lower FT3 probability is most likely due to a lower TT3. There are studies that can be evaluated that FT3 is affected by non-diabetics in diabetic postmenopausal cases. Not only does the postmenopausal state affect the thyroid, diabetes is an additional contributor to aging. In addition, diabetes is associated with central obesity in the elderly, increasing thyroid dysfunction. In a study conducted after the evaluation of a large number

of parameters, it was concluded that the prevalence of hypothyroidism in DM2 patients, especially 45 years and older, was very high. Thyroid status should be screened in DM2 to prevent it. Exacerbation of the clinical course of the disease.

CONCLUSION:

Thyroid gland appears to be adapting its function in postmenopausal and non-diabetic diabetics. These results emphasize the evaluation and management of thyroid health and impairment in older women. However, a wider study population can be assessed to make the results more general. In postmenopausal diabetic women TT4 was significantly higher in comparison with women who are premenopausal. In cases of diabetes, FT3 and total triiodothyronine are lower significantly than non-diabetic postmenopausal women. Compared with postmenopausal diabetic cases, free triiodothyronine level was higher significantly in cases of premenopausal. It is concluded that Thyroid gland stimulate its capability in non-diabetic and diabetic postmenopausal patients. Nevertheless, work in a larger population must have a clear idea.

REFERENCES:

1. Randolph, Gregory W., Quan-Yang Duh, Keith S. Heller, Virginia A. LiVolsi, Susan J. Mandel, David L. Steward, Ralph P. Tufano, and R. Michael Tuttle, for the American Thyroid Association Surgical Affairs Committee's Taskforce on Thyroid Cancer Nodal Surgery. "The prognostic significance of nodal metastases from papillary thyroid carcinoma can be stratified based on the size and number of metastatic lymph nodes, as well as the presence of extranodal extension." *Thyroid* 22, no. 11 (2012): 1144-1152.
2. Smallridge RC, Ain KB, Asa SL, Bible KC, Brierley JD, Burman KD, Kebebew E, Lee NY, Nikiforov YE, Rosenthal MS, Shah MH. American Thyroid Association guidelines for management of patients with anaplastic

- thyroid cancer. *Thyroid*. 2012 Nov 1;22(11):1104-39.
3. Akamizu T, Satoh T, Isozaki O, Suzuki A, Wakino S, Iburi T, Tsuboi K, Monden T, Kouki T, Otani H, Teramukai S. Diagnostic criteria, clinical features, and incidence of thyroid storm based on nationwide surveys. *Thyroid*. 2012 Jul 1;22(7):661-79.
 4. Cooper, D.S., Doherty, G.M., Haugen, B.R., Kloos, R.T., Lee, S.L., Mandel, S.J., Mazzaferri, E.L., McIver, B., Pacini, F., Schlumberger, M. and Sherman, S.I., 2009. Revised American Thyroid Association management guidelines for patients with thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer: the American Thyroid Association (ATA) guidelines taskforce on thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer. *Thyroid*, 19(11), pp.1167-1214.
 5. Cooper, D.S., Doherty, G.M., Haugen, B.R., Kloos, R.T., Lee, S.L., Mandel, S.J., Mazzaferri, E.L., McIver, B., Pacini, F., Schlumberger, M. and Sherman, S.I., 2009. Revised American Thyroid Association management guidelines for patients with thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer: the American Thyroid Association (ATA) guidelines taskforce on thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer. *Thyroid*, 19(11), pp.1167-1214.
 6. Carling T, Carty SE, Ciarleglio MM, Cooper DS, Doherty GM, Kim LT, Kloos RT, Mazzaferri Sr EL, Peduzzi PN, Roman SA, Sippel RS. American Thyroid Association design and feasibility of a prospective randomized controlled trial of prophylactic central lymph node dissection for papillary thyroid carcinoma. *Thyroid*. 2012 Mar 1;22(3):237-44.
 7. Sisson TA, Freitas J, McDougall IR, Dauer LT, Hurley JR, Brierley JD, Edinboro CH, Rosenthal D, Thomas MJ, Wexler JA, Asamoah E. Radiation safety in the treatment of patients with thyroid diseases by radioiodine 131I: practice recommendations of the American Thyroid Association. *Thyroid*. 2011 Apr 1;21(4):335-46.
 8. Cooper DS, Doherty GM, Haugen BR, Kloos RT, Lee SL, Mandel SJ, Mazzaferri EL, McIver B, Sherman SI, Tuttle RM. Management guidelines for patients with thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer: The American Thyroid Association Guidelines Taskforce. *Thyroid*. 2006 Feb 1;16(2):109-42.
 9. Haugen, B.R., Alexander, E.K., Bible, K.C., Doherty, G.M., Mandel, S.J., Nikiforov, Y.E., Pacini, F., Randolph, G.W., Sawka, A.M., Schlumberger, M. and Schuff, K.G., 2016. 2015 American Thyroid Association management guidelines for adult patients with thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer: the American Thyroid Association guidelines task force on thyroid nodules and differentiated thyroid cancer. *Thyroid*, 26(1), pp.1-133.
 10. Hundahl, S.A., Fleming, I.D., Fremgen, A.M. and Menck, H.R., 1998. A National Cancer Data Base report on 53,856 cases of thyroid carcinoma treated in the US, 1985-1995. *Cancer*, 83(12), pp.2638-2648.